

A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY ON AGRICULTURAL EXPORT PROMOTION SCHEMES OF APEDA: WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO CERTAIN STATES

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Abstract:

Agriculture is the major sector that feeds the country's trade. The agriculture sector's growth is a critical driver of the country's overall economic development as approximately 50% of the country's population is involved in agriculture and allied activities. The Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development Authority (APEDA) is accountable for monitoring exports of cereals, processed foods, Animal Products, Processed fruits and vegetables, fresh fruits and vegetables, cashew, floriculture & seeds. The agency plays a critical role in enhancing India's agricultural exports by facilitating the export of various agricultural commodities and providing financial schemes for farmers and exporters. This financial schemes were not reaching the exporters properly. For this purpose, data was collected using a questionnaire, and collected data was analyzed through descriptive statistics and one sample t-test. The study found that very few exporters were making use of financial schemes provided by APEDA.

1. Introduction:

Agriculture is the backbone of the Indian economy and accounts for the largest contribution of employment and gross domestic product and a source of raw materials for industry. Trade in agricultural products is playing an important role in promoting economic development of developing countries. The export of agricultural products is accelerating of capital goods, technologies, manufactured products and other essential economic commodities for the sustainable economic growth of developing countries.

Many developing countries have a comparative advantage in the production of agricultural commodities and export of these commodities is the main source of foreign exchange earnings. In an export led growth model of trade it would be to the advantage of the developing countries, to specialize in production of those products where they have comparative advantage and to use the surplus production to earn valuable foreign exchange. Such a policy will lead to the use of trade as an engine of growth as well as in ensuring rational allocation of agricultural resources.

India has a strong comparative advantage because of its very diverse agro-climatic condition ranging from arid to heavy rainfall areas. Most of the areas have well distributed rainfall, sunshine and temperature conducive to the growth of a very wide range of tropical, sub-tropical, and temperate fruits, vegetables and flowers. There are long uninterrupted Himalayan hilly region suitable for temperate and nut crops like apples, pears, peaches and walnuts. It then gradually descends, forming sub-mountain regions and plains.

India can become one of the largest fruit and vegetable exporters in the world and can equally be a large importer given its demographic diversity. This strong footing in agriculture provides a large and varied raw material base for food processing. There should be technology up gradation, quality management, firm adherence to export commitments and acquisition of appropriate negotiation skills. Many non-traditional vegetables mainly processed & gherkins and others like asparagus, celery, bell pepper, sweet corn, green and lime beans and organically grown vegetables are also being increasingly exported. India's exports of Processed Food were worth Rs. 10065.58 Crores in 2008-09, which included the share of products like Mango Pulp worth (Rs. 752.99 Crores), dried and Preserved Vegetable (Rs. 496.42 Crores), Other Processed Fruit and Vegetables (Rs. 1371.79 Crores), Pulses (Rs. 542.32 Crores), Groundnuts (Rs. 1239.01 Crores), Guargum (Rs. 1338.99 Crores), Jaggery & Confectionary (Rs. 2004.82 Crores), Cocoa Products (Rs. 84.04 Crores), Cereal Preparations (Rs. 1100.93 Crores), Alcoholic and Non-Alcoholic Beverages (Rs. 542.54 Crores) and

Miscellaneous Preparations (Rs. 591.73 Crores). The Indian food processing industry is primarily export oriented. India's geographical situation gives it the unique advantage of connectivity to Europe, the Middle East, Japan, Singapore, Thailand, Malaysia and Korea. One such example indicating India's location advantage is the value of trade in agriculture and processed food between India and Gulf region.

1.1 APEDA and its schemes

The Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development Authority (APEDA) was established by the Government of India, under the Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development Authority Act passed by the Parliament in December, 1985. The Act (2 of 1986) came into effect from 13th February, 1986 by a notification issued in the Gazette of India: Extraordinary: Part-II [Sec. 3(ii): 13.2.1986]. The Authority replaced the Processed Food Export Promotion Council (PFEPCC)

APEDA is responsible for undertaking the —development and promotion of export of 14 agricultural and processed food products, listed in the first schedule of APEDA and has been entrusted with the task of registration and protection of the Intellectual Property rights in respect of 'Special Products' in India or Outside India; currently, only 'Special Product,' as listed in the Second Schedule to the APEDA Act is Basmati Rice. After protracted efforts, APEDA obtained GI registration for Basmati Rice in February 2016.

APEDA is mandated with the responsibility of export promotion and development of the following scheduled products:

- Fruits, Vegetables and their Products.
- Meat and Meat Products.
- Poultry and Poultry Products.
- Dairy Products.
- Confectionery, Biscuits and Bakery Products.
- Honey, Jaggery and Sugar Products.
- Cocoa and its products, chocolates of all kinds.
- Alcoholic and Non-Alcoholic Beverages.
- Cereal and Cereal Products.
- Groundnuts, Peanuts and Walnuts.
- Pickles, Papads and Chutneys.
- Guar Gum.
- Floriculture and Floriculture Products
- Herbal and Medicinal Plants

APEDA provides financial assistance to its registered member exporters under the following schemes

- Scheme for Market Development
- Scheme for Infrastructure Development
- Scheme for Quality Development
- Scheme for Research and Development
- Scheme for Transport Assistance

Scheme for Market Development

Under the Market Development scheme, APEDA works to develop and disseminate databases, market intelligence by online platforms and e-commerce platforms to permit direct linkages among stakeholders to make a strong database for taking the right decisions about markets, products and dissemination of such information to various stakeholders. This component provides assistance to recognized exporters of APEDA through; product development, research & development, enhancement of traceability, new market, conducting feasibility studies, registration of brand, intellectual property rights (IPR) outside India and trail shipment for fresh horticultural products' for the enhancement in the export of agro-processed food

products.

Scheme for Infrastructure Development

APEDA provides financial assistance to improve export infrastructure under the development scheme of export infrastructure. The development of suitable infrastructures is very important for the growth and export of the agro-food sector. APEDA found loopholes in post-harvest export infrastructure facilities, resulting in colossal wastage and inefficiency in exporting agro-processed food products.

The scheme covers fresh produce and processed food products and emphasis; —setting and handling post-harvest facilities, reduce losses caused due to spoilage, quality production of agro products, financial assistance to the exporters, setting up of infrastructure, pack house facilities, equipment for Collection, cleaning, washing, sorting/ grading, pre-cooling, packing, cold storage, handheld NIR instrument, hot water dip treatment (HWDT), cableway system for handling of crops like banana, pre shipment treatment facilities, vapour heat treatment (VHT), compliance to Phytosanitary requirements for the control of plant diseases especially in agricultural crops of importing countries, processing facilities.

Scheme for Quality Development

Under this component assistance is provided to National Referral Laboratory (NRL), other govt. / public sector/institutions for residues monitoring of agrochemicals, control pesticides, testing of water, soil, veterinary drugs, aflatoxins, hormones, toxins, heavy metals, microbial count, procuring handheld devices, implementation and certification of quality, food safety management systems, training in India and abroad for attending seminars/workshops/ outreach programs, installation of quality management systems, laboratory testing equipment, handheld devices for capturing farm level peripheral coordinates for traceability systems and testing of samples, standardization & harmonization with International standards for adoption of International Standards, strengthening of technical and managerial skills, preparation of manuals brochures and guidelines for export activities etc. which helps in achieving such prescribed standards for export. This component is also focused on ensuring quality and food safety compliance; financial assistance is extended to APEDA registered members. Financial assistance is also extended to upgrade recognized labs, in-house lab equipment, innovative ideas providing infrastructure and quality improvement in India's agriculture and processed food sector.

Scheme for Research and Development

Assistance to support Research and development for export efforts through R & D organizations in Government sector . Assistance to exports, Trade Associations , Cooperative institutions etc. to support relevant research & development for export enhancement through R & D organizations in cooperative/ private sector .

Scheme for Transport Assistance

Assistance to support transport facilities for the exporters. Under this component assistance is provided for cool storage vehicles, transport facilities by air ways, water ways which helps for the easy exporting activities.

Review of Literature

This section of the paper deals with analysing the existing literature on the current research topic to identify the untouched area.

Nain , Rashmi Singh and Mishra (2017), examined that the awareness regarding governmental initiatives has always been among the major hindering factors to take full advantage of the developmental efforts. The study was conducted in two districts (Palwal and Faridabad) of southern Haryana (vulnerable to Earthquake, Industrial & Chemical Disaster, Floods, Drought, Accidents, Fire, Health related Disaster, Hailstorm, Bio Terrorism etc.) shows that farmers awareness level regarding the agricultural insurance schemes was found at lowest ebb in terms of its components and sub components. Number of constraints were reported by the respondent farmers hindering the acquisition of Agricultural Insurance Scheme which need immediate attention of the stakeholders to fulfill the lofty dreams set forth in respect of the newly launched schemes.

Vibha Pai Angle (2018), conducted a study in North Goa to examine the awareness level on agricultural schemes among the farmers. They collected the responses from 150 farmers by distributing the questionnaire. Both primary and secondary data were used to collect the data. The researchers found that 62% of agriculturist do not have Krishi cards. Largely the farmers use their own funds to carry out their agricultural activities and they don't take the help of government agricultural loans. Only 26% of farmers take loan for buying the agricultural seeds. The researchers finally concluded that the majority of agriculturist do not avail schemes due to complexities involved in the schemes.

Singh, Bhaskar, Shehrawat (2020), conducted research on farmers' awareness and performance about agriculture development schemes in Haryana. The study was conducted from randomly selected districts of Hisar and Fatehabad in Haryana state during the year 2018-19. Questionnaire was collected from 100 farmers of selected district. The results indicated that 86.00 per cent of the farmers were aware about the crops included under PMFBY followed by awareness about the premium paid for insurance of the crops (72.00%) and e-NAM facility (72.00%). As for as soil health card scheme is concerned, 68.00 per cent of the respondents have awareness followed by know about the benefits of the scheme (56.00%). Majority of the respondents (87.00%) were of view that Pradhan Mantri Fasal Beema Yojana, Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchai Yojana (Per Drop More Crops) is performing good. 64.00%, 52.00% and 50.00% of the respondents viewed that ATMA, NFSM and MIDH schemes respectively are also performing good

Aditya Shehrawat, Nidhi Sharma, Pardip Shehrawat and Sandeep Bhakar (2020) , investigated the awareness and performance of farmers about crop insurance and agricultural development schemes in Hisar and Fatehabad districts of Haryana state. Data was collected via interview schedule from 100 farmers selected randomly from these two districts. The study revealed that 86 per cent of the farmers were found aware about the crops included under Pradhan Mantri Fasal Beema Yojana (PMFBY) followed by premium paid for insurance of the crops (72 %). The data regarding awareness of Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchai Yojana (PMKSY) showed that more than half of the respondents had aware about PMKSY. However, majority of respondents (above 64 %) were found not aware about subsidy pattern under scheme and additional benefits for small farmers. Performance of agricultural development schemes predicts that majority of the respondent (87 %) viewed that is performing well. Only 13 per cent of the respondents viewed that the scheme is performing not so good. In case of PMKSY, majority of the respondents (72 %) had opinion that the scheme is performing good. About half of the respondents (52 %) viewed that Agricultural Mechanization for *In-Situ* Crop Residue Management is performing good. The awareness regarding promotion of Agricultural Mechanization for *In-Situ* Crop Residue Management (CRM) indicated that two-third respondents had awareness about the scheme and 62 per cent of them agreed that custom hiring centre established under the scheme.

Jain, Srivatsa (2021), conducted research on government schemes on agriculture by considering India. All these projects target at increasing investment, continuous profits flow and employ parts of domestic importance. The Indian Government introduces various schemes to support farmers in every manner and to increase employment in country side areas where maximum of the population depends on farming practices. These government schemes improve the soil condition, plant matter and to rise the net profit of the farmers so to grasp quality prices. The study was based on the brief discussion of the various yojanas and schemes provided by Indian Government for wellbeing of farmer as they are not only the food provider but the produce from the agriculture also adds a huge amount to the (GDP) Gross Domestic Products of India. This study helped in the development and awareness to the individuals that are mainly depend on the farming for their living.

Dr. M. Mahesh Kumar, D. Gnanamani (2022), investigated that the welfare of farmers has always been the top priority of the Government of India. Government takes major initiative in order to achieve the goals, benefits of farmers and economic development by providing various schemes. The study assessed awareness and impact of government schemes for farmers in Coimbatore city, Tamilnadu state in India. Convince sampling technique was used to select 100 farmers in

Coimbatore city. Also, the study aim to find out the awareness of the farmers, level of satisfaction and opinion of farmers and issues of farmers regarding agricultural government schemes. This study concluded that every farmers have to know about the schemes provided by government and government should make more efficiency to make aware of the schemes and get benefits by all the farmers in an easy mode of reach.

Manas Kumar Sethi, Dr. Santosh Kumar Biswal (2023), examined the awareness of farmers towards the agricultural schemes of government on Dhenkanal district, Odisha. In this study they identified that due to lack of awareness, some farmers are unable to get the benefits of government schemes. Out of the total respondents only 55.6% of the farmers are having awareness about the agricultural schemes. The major source of awareness to the farmers is television followed by newspaper and radio. Proper education and training are required for getting the benefits of welfare schemes and overall development of farmers.

Saurabh Tiwari, K.S. Kadian, H.R. Meena, M.S. Nain, Sweety Mukherjee, Amandeep Ranjan (2023), the study was conducted to analyse the effect of Saansad Adarsh Gram Yojana (SAGY) on farmers' awareness of different agricultural schemes during 2021. The center and state government-sponsored schemes under the SAGY were taken into consideration. As per the need of farmers, 25 schemes were included as the indicator for awareness in the study. The investigation was carried out in two blocks of the Varanasi district of Uttar Pradesh state. A significant difference was seen in awareness among the farmers of model and non-model villages. Among crop-based schemes, almost 70% of farmers of model villages were aware of the soil health card which was highest followed by *Paramparagat Krishi Vikash Yojana* (66%) and financial assistance for improved seeds(65%). Sixty percent of farmers of model villages were aware of the artificial insemination of animals scheme which was highest followed by the national livestock mission (18.67 %). In model villages, the majority of the farmers were in the category of high and medium levels of awareness. Only 14.67 % of farmers were in the category of low level of awareness but from the non-model villages, the majority of farmers were in the category of low level of awareness.

Rahimi and Artukoğlu (2021), conducted the research on problems facing agricultural product exporters and solutions from Afghanistan. There is lack of marketing services; the inadequacy of government support; taxes and customs clearance; transit transportation problems; the problem of adaptation to the global marketing system; ongoing civil war and security problems; problems in commercial relations with neighbors; problems related to education and communication; and lack of quality control systems. The authors also found the solutions for these problems include effective and appropriate marketing services; following correct and reasonable policies regarding incentives to investors, tariffs, and customs fees; strengthening the country's economic infrastructure; construction of highways and establishment of an appropriate transit transportation system; increasing security measures; and increasing the added value of domestic export items. Eliminating the problems of exporters will increase the export potential of the country and enable it to be used better.

Akdoğan, et al (2011), investigated on problems faced by exporting firms. The aim of this study is to determine the problems encountered by the exporting firms which are important for the economic purposes. In this respect, more specifically, this study investigates the problems encountered by the exporting firms operating in the city of Kayseri in Turkey, and also their perceptions related to this issue. The aim is so related to measure those encountered and perceived problems of the exporting firms in terms of their firm characteristics. In line with the aim, the study has been carried out through collecting primary data from the exporting in Kayseri. As the primary data indicates, the exporting firms operating in the city of Kayseri encounter some exporting problems related to target market determination mistakes, exchange rate fluctuations, the price competition of the Chinese products.

Abdulrahman Al-Aali (1995), conducted research on obstacles facing Saudi Arabian food and chemical exporters in Saudi Arabia. The exporters identified that the single most important obstacle perceived by the sample exporters is fierce competition in foreign markets. Competition is followed

by high cost of imported raw materials, absence of information about foreign markets, wide fluctuations in the foreign exchange rate, and high overseas transportation costs. They also identified eight categories of the obstacles such as market information, competition, shipping, government policy, foreign market risks, export procedures, production/marketing cost, and internal/technical problems.

From the analysis of existing literature, it reveals that only a few studies have focused on financial schemes provided for the exporters and no studies have focused on schemes provided by APEDA for agricultural and processed food product exporters. So the present study is intended to analyze the descriptive study on agricultural export promotion schemes of APEDA in selected state regarding the awareness about the schemes among the exporters and its impact.

Research questions

Based on the literature gap the study framed the following research questions:

1. What is the awareness regarding the export promotion schemes among exporters?
2. What is the problems of exporters regarding export promotion schemes by APEDA?

Research Objectives

With the help of research questions study framed the following two objectives:

1. To study the awareness regarding the export promotion schemes among exporters?
2. To analyze the problems of exporters regarding export promotion schemes by APEDA?

Hypotheses

To achieve the objectives study framed the following hypotheses are developed:

1. H_0 – “The exporters are not having awareness regarding export promotion schemes”.
2. H_0 – “ There is no problem of exporters regarding export promotion schemes by APEDA”.

Data and Methodology:

The present study is empirically based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data is collected through a survey method with the help of structured questionnaire from the exporters in Karnataka, Kerala and Tamil Nadu. For data collection exporters were selected based on convenience sampling method. The respondent's details were indicated in the following table.

SI No	Respondents (State)	No. of Questionnaires distributed	No. of Responses collected	The response rate in %
1	Karnataka	12	09	75%
2	Kerala	19	14	73%
3	Tamil Nadu	16	13	81%
	Total	47	36	76%

Source : Author compiled

The exporters are identified in the EOUs such as Phalada Agro Research Foundation Pvt Ltd, Mother India Farms, Eco Agri India, Green Chem, Tata Coffee Limited, HillGreen Plantatins Pvt Ltd, Sri Mata Bio Source, NKG JAYANTI, Sri Anandateertha Aromatics Pvt Ltd, Namdhari Seeds Pvt Ltd so on.

Results and Discussions:

This section of the paper deals with analyzing the results of primary data and discuss the results to prove or disprove the hypotheses of the study.

Awareness variables regarding export promotion schemes	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-value	Sig (two tailed test)
Awareness regarding registration under APEDA to get benefits of the schemes	36	3.9167	1.104518	4.977	.000
Awareness about financial benefits for exporting different agri products	36	4.5278	.99960	9.170	.000
Awareness regarding facilities provided by APEDA under financial schemes	36	4.4722	.81015	10.903	.000
Awareness about financial schemes will be given both cash and kind	36	3.9722	.87786	6.645	.000
Awareness about opening of separate bank account for sanctioning of grants under financial schemes	36	4.5278	.87786	10.442	.000
Awareness of physical inspection report for release of grant	36	4.5278	.87786	10.442	.000
Awareness about penalty for non payment of financial grants taken from APEDA.	36	4.1111	1.34754	4.947	.000

Table No.2 shows the results of one sample t test at the 5% significance level in regarding awareness level in regarding awareness regarding the export promotion schemes among exporters and indicates all the awareness variables shows the p value less than 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis “H₀ - The exporters are not having awareness regarding export promotion schemes” is rejected and alternative hypothesis “H₁ - The exporters are having awareness regarding export promotion schemes” is accepted. It means the exporters are having the awareness about the financial schemes provided by APEDA.

Results of one sample T-test regarding problems of exporters regarding export promotion schemes by APEDA

Problem variables regarding export promotion schemes	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-value	Sig (two tailed test)
Facing network issues in the website of APEDA for the access regarding financial schemes	36	4.1111	1.25988	5.292	.000
Financial assistance given by APEDA is not reaching isolated region properly	36	4.6944	.62425	16.286	.000
Common infrastructure storage facility are leading to misuse of agri products	36	4.2500	1.25071	5.997	.000
Facing difficulty in maintaining quality of agri products constantly	36	4.5556	.73463	12.705	.000
Financial assistance schemes provided by APEDA are not sufficient for targeting your agri products at overseas market	36	4.4722	.69636	12.685	.000
Facing difficulty in getting financial assistance regarding transportation	36	4.6667	.95618	10.458	.000
Capital formation for exporting process is difficult	36	4.2222	1.26742	5.786	.000

Table No 3 shows the results of one sample t-test at the 5% significance level in regarding perception on the problems of exporters regarding export promotion schemes by APEDA and which indicates all the variables shows the p value less than 0.05. Hence null hypothesis

H_0 – “ There is no problem faced by exporters regarding export promotion schemes by APEDA” and alternative hypothesis “ H_1 – There is problem faced by exporters regarding export promotion schemes by APEDA” is accepted. It means the financial assistance for export promotion provided for the exporters are facing many problems to get the benefits of these schemes.

Findings:

This section of the paper reveals the outcomes of the study in the form of findings which are presented here based on objectives and general observation made during the study:

Based on Objectives:

Concerning first objectives study found that the exporters are having positive rate of awareness about the export promotion schemes given by APEDA. But even though they have awareness they are not properly enjoying the financial assistance given by the institute, which has led to various problems to the exporters for the exporting of agricultural and processed food products.

Concerning second objectives study found that opined that the exporters need proper solution to their problems which they are facing through APEDA. If these problems are solved the exporters can place their products in overseas market, the financial assistance given by them will help them to arrange for the capital, can maintain good quality of products, can also have proper common storage facilities and further it helps the exporters to achieve their objectives.

Based on Observations:

The study found that the registered exporters under APEDA is not enjoying the financial assistance completely. Even though they have awareness about the export promotion schemes given by APEDA the exporters are investing their own funds for further fulfillments of their needs for exporting activities. If the APEDA's financial assistance is reaching the exporters properly the exporting activities can be improved and wastage of agricultural products can be minimized. This will also helps to create a supportive environment to achieve Sustainable Development Goals set by UNOs.

Conclusions:

Exporting agricultural food products and processed foods are playing vital role across the world. The exporters who have registered under APEDA are getting financial assistance such as market development schemes, quality development schemes, infrastructure development schemes, transportation schemes and research and development schemes which will help them to export these products across the world. Finally, the study concludes that the findings of the study is one of the evident for APEDA for getting solution for the problems which are faced by the exporters. This will help the exporters to get proper utilization of financial assistance and also protect the agricultural and processed food products from the wastage while exporting across the world. It will also indirectly contributes to the Sustainable Development Goals set by United Nation Organisation.